

Possible Distributions of Negative-Dark Matter in Various Galaxies, and New Research for Some Peculiar Galaxies

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Abstract:

The general assumption of galaxy formation is origin of the uneven density distribution. This is certainly the most important thing. But this alone cannot explain the diversity of galaxy shapes, especially the Hoag's Object. Here we propose that dark matter is negative matter and discuss distribution and observations of negative-dark matter in Milky Way, and quantitatively predict that the negative dark matter exists most likely between visible spiral arms. From this we may explain different shapes of various galaxies, the Hoag's Object, and the arm stability of spiral galaxies, etc. Further, we predict the presence of corresponding negative matter black holes, and possible

similar cosmic mass dipole and try to explain galaxy AM 0644-741. It may estimate that the presence of galaxies made entirely of the negative matter will be 4.36 times of known galaxies. This interaction alternating between positive and negative matters, gravity and repulsion will show the complexity of galaxies and the Universe.

Keywords: galaxy, dark matter, negative matter, distribution, Milky Way, observation.

Introduction

Galaxy is very important in astronomy (Binney & Tremaine, 1987; Binney & Merrifield, 1998; Longair, 1998). According to the Hubble galaxy classification system, general galaxies are divided into Fig.1.

It is usually considered as the spiral galaxies, including the Milky Way at 77%, elliptical (E) galaxies at 20%, Irregular (Irr) galaxies at 3%. Moreover, various active galaxies and so on have yet to be studied.

Figure 1. The Hubble Galaxy Classification System

Galactic dynamics is related to celestial mechanics, classical statistics and plasma physics, and discussed equilibrium and stability in collisionless system, disk dynamics and spiral

structure, collisions and encounter in galaxies and so on (Binney & Tremaine, 1987). Stellar structure and evolution theory are the basis for our understanding of the information on all aspects of the galaxy (Binney & Merrifield, 1998). The general assumption of galaxy formation is origin of the uneven density distribution. Galaxy diversity attributed to the influence of the environment (Oemler, 1974). This is certainly the most important thing. But this alone cannot explain the diversity of galaxy shapes, especially the Hoag's Object. In this paper, based on dark matter as the negative matter, we discuss distribution and observations of negative-dark matter in Milky Way and various galaxies, and explain different shapes of galaxies.

Distribution and Observations of Negative-Dark Matter in Milky Way

Based on Dirac negative energy, Einstein mass-energy relation and principle of equivalence, we proposed the negative matter as the simplest model of unified dark matter and dark energy. All theories are known, only mass includes positive and negative. Because there is repulsion between positive matter and negative matter, so which is invisible dark matter, and repulsion as dark energy. It may explain many phenomena of dark matter and dark energy (Chang, 2007,2011,2013, 2014a,b, 2017, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022a, 2023a,b). We derived that the rotational velocity of galaxy is approximate constant, and an evolutionary ratio between total matter and usual matter from 1 to present 11.82 or 7.88 (Chang, 2023a,b). We found that some proofs of the positive mass theorem have all certain premises: an isolated gravitational system and infinite space, but both are all impossible. Therefore, the negative matter cannot be restricted. We discussed some simple estimations of the positive matter theorem, which agree from astronomy to particles (Chang, 2022a). And Bondi's results are also wrong. We calculated the accelerated expansion at 9.760 billion years. The mechanism of inflation is origin of positive-negative matters created from nothing, whose expansion is exponential due to

strong interactions at small microscopic scales. We proposed specifically some possible ways on observe dark matter in the Milky Way. Many observatories should be able to observe these results. We researched some basic problems in cosmology: Possible mechanism of missing antimatter, the origins of mass and charge, etc (Chang, 2023b). The negative matter as a candidate of unified dark matter and dark energy is not only the simplest, and is calculable, observable and testable, and may be changed and developed.

Because dark matter is 25.96%, and dark energy is 69.2% in Universe (Adam et al. 2016; Tanabashi et al. 2018), as long as there is some dark matter or dark energy in the solar system, general relativity, even Newtonian's gravity theory can not be so accurate, therefore, there are not necessarily dark matter and dark energy in the solar system, and dark energy cannot distribute uniformly in the whole space (Chang, 2023a).

Georgelin and Georgelin (1976) proposed a famous model of four-arm segments in Milky Way. Recently, Reid and Zheng (2020) researched to show that the Milky Way structure is a barred spiral galaxy with four spiral arms (Fig.2).

Figure 2. The Milky Way Structure

Hao, et al. (2021) discussed evolution of the local spiral structure of the Milky Way revealed by open clusters. By the astrometric satellite Gaia, Xu, et al. (2021), delineated the Galactic spiral structure, and investigated the local spiral structure.

There must have dark matter in the Milky Way. We should closely observe the dark regions of the Milky Way (Fig.2), which could be three categories: gas cloud, black hole, or dark matter. The black holes form some spherical regions, while gas cloud and dark matter may not be completely regular. When the Earth is in different positions of the solar system throughout a year, the background stars of these regions will be respectively constant, gravitational lensing, or opposite repulsive lensing if negative matter as dark matter. The both angles of deflection are:

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{4G(\pm M)}{c^2 R}, \quad (1)$$

in which R is the same for a black hole, while R for negative matter is not necessarily the same. Many observatories should be able to observe these differences (Chang, 2023b). Further, we predict that the place where negative dark matter exists most likely between visible spiral arms, and the closer to the edge, the more likely. It is consistent with about one-third of the matter in the solar neighborhood must be dark matter (Binney & Tremaine, 1987). This produces the stability of the spiral arms, and approximate stable state in Milky Way. We look forward to the early results of the astronomers.

Discussion of Basic Galaxies Based on Negative-Dark Matter

Based on the negative matter is namely dark matter, we discuss basic galaxies. The total energy includes three parts: one of the positive matter, one of negative matter, and their repulsion force:

$$E_t = \sum_i m_i^+ c^2 - \sum_{ij} \frac{Gm_i^+ m_j^+}{r_{ij}} - \sum_k m_k^- c^2 - \sum_{kl} \frac{Gm_k^- m_l^-}{r_{kl}} + \sum_{ik} \frac{Gm_i^+ m_k^-}{r_{ik}}. \quad (2)$$

General case $r_{ik} \gg r_{ij} \approx r_{kl}$, assume that $M_+ = M_-$, so $E_+ \ll E_-$.

Combining the different structures of galaxies, we analyze the possible distributions and ratios of positive and negative matters, and their evolutions. Negative matter is mixed with general matter, and have different distributions, in which gravity and repulsive cross each other. This may explain the different shapes of galaxies, and predict some possible phenomena.

The spiral galaxies have rotation, which will turn into a secular instability by Jeans instability and Maclaurin spheroid, etc (Binney & Tremaine, 1987). The spiral structures may be Lin-Shu density wave theory, chaotic spiral arm and tidal arm, the spiral detonation wave, etc.

Figure 3. M51

The spiral galaxies are similar the Milky Way, and the negative-dark matter exists probably between different arms. Positive and negative matters intersect, and both seem to equal. Such $M_+ \approx M_-$, therefore, the rotation curves of spiral galaxies are approximate constants, and are consistent with the measured curves (Rubin, 1983; Chang, 2023a,b). They include

Whirlpool Galaxy M51 (Fig.3), M81(NGC 3031) (Fig. 4) (Petersen & Brandt, 1998), NGC 5364 (Sc), NGC 598 (M33), NGC 1300 (SBb), NGC 3256 [Sb(pec)], etc (Binney & Tremaine, 1987).

Figure 4. M81 (NGC 3031)

The barred spiral galaxies, as NGC 1300(SBb) and NGC 7741(SBc) (Binney & Merrifield, 1998), are not symmetry. They are possibly the asymmetrical distributions of positive and negative matters.

For the elliptical (E) galaxies, the dark matter haloes exist probably (Binney & Tremaine, 1987; Binney & Merrifield, 1998). The positive and negative matters may be evenly distributed, or be slightly more positive matter, as NGC 3379(E0) (Fig.5), NGC 4261(E3), NGC4486= M87(E0), NGC3377(E6) (Binney & Merrifield, 1998).

Figure 5. NGC3379

For the irregular (Irr) galaxies, perhaps both positive and negative matter distributions are also irregular.

It is known that the relation between light L and mass M is $\lg(L/L_0)=b\lg(M/M_0)$, ($3.5 < b < 4$). And the mass-to-light ratios M/L are bigger ($20 \sim 40$) for the elliptical galaxies, and are smaller (< 10) for Sc galaxies and Irr galaxies. If L is the same, bigger M/L , $M = M_+ - M_-$ will be bigger. It indicates less negative matter. This is consistent with our prediction.

Some Peculiar Galaxies

Hoag's Object (Fig.6) is a perfectly symmetric ring galaxy, whose diameter is about 120,000 light-years, and the bright rings of billions of blue stars form a perfect circle around a smaller, denser sphere of red stars. In the dark gap between the two stellar rings, there is a ring.

Figure 6. Hoag's object (NASA/ESA/Hubble)

The ring galaxies exist for less than 0.1% of all known galaxies. Hogg believes that the strange ring of this galaxy is only an optical illusion caused by gravitational lensing. But, later studies with better telescopes refuted the idea. Ford, et al. (1987) ruled out several earlier hypotheses on the origin of the ring, and proposed the new hypothesis that Hoag's object owes its structure

to a major accretion event at least 2-3 Gyr ago. Then astronomers should be able to look some of the consequences of the accident through radio telescopes. But no such evidence was found.

Finkelman, et al. (2011) presented new photometric and spectroscopic observations of the famous Hoag's Object, a peculiar ring galaxy with a central roundish core. The nature of Hoag's Object is still under controversy. Previous studies demonstrated that a major accretion event that took place at least 2-3 Gyr ago can account for the observational evidence. These new data are used to demonstrate that Hoag's Object is a relatively isolated system surrounded by a luminous quasi-spiral pattern and a massive. The main stellar body is an old, mildly triaxial elliptical galaxy with very high angular momentum. They reviewed previous formation scenarios of Hoag's Object in light of the new data and conclude that the peculiar morphology could not represent a late phase in barred early-type galaxies evolution. In addition, no observational evidence supports late merging events in the evolution of the galaxy, although further tests are required before safely dismissing this idea. Combining all the information, they proposed a new scenario where the elliptical core formed in the early Universe with the HI disc forming shortly after the core by prolonged 'cold' accretion of primordial gas from the intergalactic medium. The low gas density does not allow intense star formation to occur everywhere in the disc, but only along a tightly wound spiral pattern of enhanced density induced by the triaxial gravitational potential. According to this view, the physical mechanism that forms rings in Hoag-like galaxies is closely linked with that in some non-barred disc galaxies, although the formation and evolution of both classes of galaxies are clearly distinct. Whether or not this unique evolutionary track is related to the galaxy residing in an environment remains to be solved.

Brosch, et al. (2013) presented new HI observations of Hoag's Object obtained with the Westerbork Synthesis Radio Telescope (WSRT). The data show that the luminous optical ring around the elliptical body has a bright HI

counterpart that shares the kinematical properties of the optical ring. The entire HI structure is twice as large as the optical ring and shows a mild warp in its outer regions relative to the inner ring. They reported on a newly identified SDSS optical companion galaxy, and main conclusion is that the HI detected in Hoag's Object shows no indication that this galaxy has experienced a recent (less than ~ 1 Gyr ago) accretion event. At least one of the two additional HI detected objects does not have an optical counterpart. One possibility is that this object is an HI filament left over from an interaction shaping Hoag's Object, in which case this interaction must also have occurred at least 1-2 Gyr ago.

So far, Hoag's Object is still one of the most beautiful mysteries in the Universe.

According to our theory (Chang, 2007, 2011, 2013, 2014a,b, 2017, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022a, 2023a,b), this flat galaxy may be a ring structure with negative matter in the middle, similar to a sandwich structure. Both sides are positive matter. Positive matter and negative matter aggregate each other into stable rings. But, the middle core of the galaxy is so massive, when the surrounding negative matter is subtracted, it can still attract the outer layer of positive matter.

Figure 7. Galaxy NGC 6782

Further, it includes various ring galaxies: core ring (ESO 565-11), inner ring (IC 5240), outer ring (NGC 1543), and three rings at the same time (NGC 6782) (Fig.7) (Buta & Combes 1996; Binney & Merrifield, 1998).

Many ring galaxies may be explained, but they all have certain unexplained observed phenomena.

Figure 8. Black Eye Galaxy M64

The black dust belt in Black Eye Galaxy (M64) (Fig.8), and various black areas are probably the negative-dark matter.

Guo, et al. (2020) reported 19 dwarf galaxies that could consist mainly of baryons, and provided observational evidence that could challenge the formation theory of low-mass galaxies within the framework of standard cosmology.

Galaxy AM 0644-741 (Fig.9) shows an ellipsoid circular galaxy, whose diameter is about 130,000 light-years. In Fig.10 it is currently believed that the left-below of this circular galaxy is an ellipsoidal galaxy, which may have crossed and formed a circular galaxy hundreds of millions of years ago.

We propose the negative-dark matter can also form black holes, which are mutually repulsion with general matter. If positive and negative

black holes form double cores, they may produce huge similar cosmic electric dipoles, and have various corresponding effects.

Figure 9. Galaxy AM 0644-741

Figure 10. Wide view on the circular galaxy AM 0644-741 and its surroundings

If the dark region corresponding to the bright region is a black hole, the black hole will have a huge gravity, and this system will be unstable; if this is the negative-dark matter, it will be repulsion between each other, and the structure will be stable.

Assume that $M_+ \approx M_-$, let $d_m = MR_{\pm}$ which will increase along with time, then the mass

dipole potential $\varphi = \frac{d_m}{R^2}$, the mass dipole field

$E = \frac{2d_m}{R^3}$ and corresponding total mass dipole radiation is:

$$I = \frac{2\ddot{d}_m}{3c^3} = \frac{2M\ddot{R}_\pm}{3c^3}. \quad (3)$$

Since M is very large, so as long as R changes, radiation I will be very large. We can obtain the

similar magnetic moment $M = \frac{d_m \times V}{2c}$, and

corresponding similar magnetic field $A = \frac{M}{R^2}$

(Landau & Lifshitz, 1975).

It is that the binary stars and binary black holes develop to the dipole of the positive and

negative matters, whose theoretical basis should be the nonlinear hydrodynamics.

Cartwheel galaxy is a beautiful ring galaxy (Fig.11), in which a central core of old stars and a bright ring of young stars are connected by a thin gas and stellar bridge. The cause of the ring is currently thought to be a breaking galaxy that smashed through the Cartwheel.

Zwicky II 28 circular galaxy (Fig. 12) lacks a central core and has a bright ring.

Arp (Atlas of Peculiar Galaxies) 10 are two interacting galaxies (Fig.13), each galaxy with a ring, are almost certainly the result of the center-to-center collisions between the two precursors. Pairs of galaxy accelerate each other and are about to interact.

Mayall object (Fig.14) is two galaxies collision during the formation of a circular galaxy.

Figure 11. Cartwheel galaxy

Figure 12. Zwicky II 28

Figure 13. Galaxy Arp 10

Figure 14. Mayall object

Active galaxies at about 2% are of active nuclei (Robson, 1996). We believe that they may be the results of the intense interactions between positive and negative matters. And corresponding accreting disk theory will be corrected and developed.

Fig.15 Galaxy NGC 5128

For two lobes in radio galaxies, they are usually located almost symmetrically in the opposite direction of the nucleus, as 3C405, NGC5128 (Fig.15), more than 60,000 light-years in size, and have a pair of giant radio lobes nearly a million light-years, and judge seem to have black hole. The double lobe structure cannot always be gravity, and attraction is mutual fusion. If there is negative matter with mutually repulsion, it will form double valve, but it should not be visible.

Theoretical Developments and Conclusion

Based on the negative matter as the unified model of dark matter and dark energy (Chang, 2007,2011,2013, 2014a,b, 2017, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022a, 2023a,b), mass and charge have symmetrical theory, and include various similar electromagnetic theory, electrodynamics and QED, etc.

In general relativity Einstein (1955) and Landau, et al (1975) derived some similar formulas of electromagnetic theory, for example, the similar Lorentz formulas (Einstein, 1955):

$$\frac{d}{cdt}[(1 + \bar{\sigma})\frac{v}{c}] = grad\bar{\sigma} + \frac{\partial u}{c\partial t} - \frac{v}{c} \times rotu. \quad (4)$$

Here $\bar{\sigma} = \gamma_{44} / 2 = -\phi / c^2$, $u = i\gamma_{4\alpha}$. In this case, moving matter produces similar magnetic field, such as a rotation with angular velocity $\omega = -(rotu / 2c)$ is similar with Coriolis force.

Landau, et al. (1975) derived:

$$f = \frac{dp}{dt} = -mc^2 grad(\ln\sqrt{h}) + mc\sqrt{h}v \times rotg_{\alpha}. \quad (5)$$

Here $h = -g_{00}$, $g_{\alpha} = -g_{\alpha 0} / g_{00}$. For the negative matter, $g_{\alpha 0}$, g_{α} and $\gamma_{4\alpha}$ are different, and these formulas must be replaced by $m \rightarrow -m$.

We developed relations of electromagnetic field and gravitational field (Chang, 2015):

The above framed theory has been completed, while the no-framed theory is being explored, which includes the electromagnetic general relativity (Chang, 2005).

Based on the electromagnetic waves, we obtained the gravitational waves and their three predictions: their observations must be nonlinear waves; velocity of gravitational wave is slightly higher than the velocity of light; gravitational waves in black holes may emit and be observed (Chang, 2022b, 2023c).

When the positive and negative matters collide, their energy should be zero, but it must have a huge energy $2mc^2$ or will produce $2mc^2$.

It is known that the dwarf galaxies, as NGC1520-DF2 $M_- \approx 0$ (Guo et al. 2020). Further, we predict:

- I. The spiral galaxies $M_+ \approx M_-$.
- II. The elliptical galaxies $M_+ > M_-$.
- III. The Irregular galaxies $M_+ < M_-$.
- IV. Hoag's Object $M_+ \gg M_-$.

The known ratio of dark matter and positive matter (Adam et al. 2016; Tanabashi et al. 2018) is 25.96:4.84=5.36. If positive and negative matters are approximately equal in known galaxies, in which 4.84 will be negative matter. Such the complete negative matter galaxies will have 21.12%, thus we may estimate that the presence of galaxies made entirely of negative matter will be 21.12:4.84=4.36 times that of known galaxies. Currently these galaxies are not visible. Some known galaxies are almost dark.

In a word, the collisions, the intersections and dynamics in galaxies must consider the repulsions between the positive and negative matters.

Various bursts in astronomy, including the starburst galaxies, may probably be the results of large repulsion between positive and negative matters. This interaction alternating between positive and negative matters, gravity and repulsion will present the complexity of galaxies

and the universe. If we add again the electromagnetic fields in the universe, astronomical phenomena will be even more colorful.

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